

Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative Collaboration Agreement v1

BACKGROUND

The Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative is a collaborative project that is developing genomic resources for Australia's native plants. The central resource for this initiative will be derived from herbaria and botanic gardens (living collections) around the country. The addition of genome sequencing data would add significant value to the collections and contribute to the development of new methods and capabilities which can be adopted more extensively in the longer term.

<https://data.bioplatforms.com/organization/about/bpa-plants>

The Consortium objectives are to:

- Sequence and assemble representative Australian plant genomes across the plant tree of life to enable better conservation, utilisation and understanding of Australia's unique plant diversity;
- Build genomic capacity across Australian Botanic Gardens and Herbaria to create networks collaborating in the collection, management, dissemination and application of genomic data for Australian plants;
- Provide tools to enable genetic data to be used to identify and classify biodiversity at a range of scales and to use these tools to inform conservation management and enable better decision making.

Activities will include the generation of data and development of workflows under three broad areas:

- reference genomes,
- phylogenomics and
- conservation genomics.

The initiative operates by employing a non-exclusive collaborative approach involving researchers from over 20 different Australian organisations:

<https://data.bioplatforms.com/organization/pages/bpa-plants/consortium>

Bioplatforms Australia Ltd (Bioplatforms) provides oversight and significant resources to support the Initiative in partnership with research community co-invested resources.

RESPONSIBILITIES AND EXPECTATIONS

1. The initiative is run using a collaborative approach with collective decisions made by relevant working groups (Wet lab and Computational) and a Steering Committee. Additional working groups will be set up as needed as the initiative progresses. Oversight of the initiative is provided as needed by a Steering committee made up of individuals representing the interests of the Botanic Gardens, conservation agencies, technology, research and investment.
2. The biological samples, DNA/RNA extracts and use of data generated from this Initiative are expected to comply with the Nagoya Protocol (<https://www.cbd.int/abs/about/>). The Nagoya Protocol is an international agreement adopted under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) on access to genetic resources and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization which entered into force on 12 October, 2014.
3. Overseas collaborators requesting biological samples, DNA/RNA extracts and data generated from this Initiative are expected to comply with the Nagoya Protocol, as described above.
4. The collaborators will provide biological samples or DNA/RNA extracts for sequence analysis. Sample metadata required by the Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative will be also need

to be provided with the samples upon submission. The Living Collections and Herbarium Accession Number must be provided along with the sample metadata.

5. Collaborators will cover the costs of sample preparation and sample submission, including sample shipment.
6. Materials prepared for the Initiative should prioritise provenance living collections and individuals' samples need to be maintained so that other "omics" analyses can be done if the community so desires.
7. Unused samples will be returned to collaborators if requested, except in the case of reference genome sequencing where the sample (tissue/DNA/RNA) will be biobanked at a relevant consortium agreed facility.
8. For whole genome sequencing datasets, where the data is generated to assist with the creation of a whole genome assembly that may include the use of 'collaborator created data' (not funded by the initiative), a case-by-case assessment will be made to determine the most appropriate arrangement that ensures the totality of data is made available in a useable and timely manner.
9. Raw data will be made available to all Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative collaborative participants immediately after generation through the consortium data portal (managed by Bioplatforms). Subsequently, raw data will be made more broadly accessible, including through relevant international data repositories, as per the Consortium Data Policy (Schedule 1).
10. Sensitive data or metadata (such as GPS coordinates of rare and threatened species) will be handled using the approach applied by the Sensitive Data Service developed by the Atlas of Living Australia:
<https://www.ala.org.au/faq/data-sensitivity/>
11. Communications (scientific or general publications and presentations) that arise from this work will appropriately acknowledge collaborators' and investors' contributions as outlined in the Consortium Communications Policy (Schedule 2).
12. Bioplatforms is to be included in Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative-related correspondence with collaborative organisations both locally and internationally to ensure consistency in communication.

OTHER MATTERS

This Agreement is not intended to create any partnership, agency or other relationship between the parties under which any of them may be taken to be responsible for the acts, omissions or debts of the other.

Nothing in this Agreement shall preclude any party from entering into other arrangements or collaborations with other persons or organisations in the areas covered by this agreement.

COLLABORATIVE AGREEMENT

This is a collaborative agreement between the Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative, signed by Bioplatforms Australia on behalf of the Initiative, and
from.....

Collaborator

Bioplatforms Australia Ltd
Level 4 Building F7B
Research Park Drive
Macquarie University NSW 2109
ABN: 40 125 905 599

Signed

Print name.....

Date.....

Bioplatforms Australia Ltd on behalf the Genomics for Australian Plants Initiative

Signed

Print name.....

Date.....